

A SOCIOLOGICAL STUDY OF JOB SATISFACTION AMONG POLICE OFFICIALS IN UT CHANDIGARH

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Paper Received On: 21 JUNE 2023

Peer Reviewed On: 30 JUNE 2023

Published On: 01 JULY 2023

Abstract

Although job satisfaction among police officers is a crucial issue for managing police forces, there is not enough research on the subject, particularly in India. Job satisfaction in law enforcement is crucial because it encourages the continuity of a competent and cohesive police force that works well together, adheres to proper policies and procedures, and offers the services required by the public. The corrective and statutory balance in society is crucially maintained by police personnel. But due to the nature of the job, police service has historically been regarded as one of the most demanding and stressful professions. The present paper focussed on level of job satisfaction. An attempt was made to know the level of job satisfaction among the respondents using 20 statements adapted from Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire. Job satisfaction was measured on various aspects, financial benefits, working conditions, work policies and public image. A majority of the respondents had low level of job satisfaction on major issues but there were some components like promotion policy, ability to enhance skills Head Constables showed more dissatisfaction.

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Introduction

There isn't enough research on the subject, especially in India, despite the fact that managing police forces must take work satisfaction among police officers into account. Research on job satisfaction in the police is essential because unsatisfied employees may have adverse effects on their services. Bennett (1997) has maintained "job satisfaction is a neglected but important and timely topic in police studies". According to Dantzker (1994), the literature on police job

satisfaction is methodologically and thematically restricted. Because it encourages the continuity of a competent and cohesive police force that works well together, adheres to proper policies and procedures, and offers the services required by the public, job satisfaction in law enforcement is crucial. According to Violanti and Aron (1994), high levels of job satisfaction are positively correlated with police officers' psychological health. Police officers who have low levels of job satisfaction may continually look for employment elsewhere (Buzawa et al. 1994; Zhao et al. 1999). According to Hoath et al. (1998), the following are some justifications for why job satisfaction is crucial for police organisations: One is that poor job performance may be impacted by employee attitudes, particularly low levels of job satisfaction, which can have an impact on both the amount and calibre of law enforcement services a company offers. Second, unfavourable police attitudes about their work may have a negative impact on the public's opinions and perceptions of a law enforcement agency and its officers, damaging police-community relations. The third justification is that a police organisation has a moral duty to care for its staff members and encourage professional attitudes among them. Fourth, job satisfaction encourages reduced stress and stress-related symptoms like absenteeism, burnout, and drunkenness. On the other hand, it is argued that when police personnel are satisfied with their job, they have lower stress level, less absenteeism and turnover. According to Lord et al. (1991), there is evidence which supports that the law enforcement is a highly stressful profession. Police administration have shown that job satisfaction has important influence on work related outcomes (job performance, commitment and turnover rates) and relationship between police and public (Agho et al. 1993; Kang and Nalla 2011; Lee and Moon, 2011; Yang et al. 2012). It is argued that negative approach of police officials toward work can negatively affect their job performance. Work experience is one of the significant factors that influences the job satisfaction (Kanchana et al. 2012). Yun et al. (2015) have revealed that the older officer with longer experience has higher turnover intent. Buzawa (1984) has found a negative association between tenure and satisfaction. The more experienced officers have lower levels of satisfaction. Johnson (2012) has revealed that the longer the officers' tenure, the lower the job satisfaction levels. Spector (1997) says that older workers are more satisfied with their jobs. The longer work duration is associated with higher job satisfaction because of associated rewards. Clark et al. (1996) and Oshagbemi (2000), have expressed similar views that individuals with longer service often express greater job satisfaction as they feel that their job resemble their needs. Bedeian et al. (1992) have found that

tenure is a more consistent indicator of job satisfaction than age. Rostami et al. (2022) didn't find significant differences in the subscales of job satisfaction between male and female police officers in Sweden.

Methodology

One of the major objectives of present study is

- To examine the level of job satisfaction among police officials posted at different police stations at U.T Chandigarh.

Materials and Methods

The present study focused on medium and lower rank male police officials i.e. Inspector, Sub-Inspector, Assistant- Sub Inspector, Head-Constable posted in sixteen police stations in UT Chandigarh. Out of total strength of 449 male police officials in sixteen police stations, 50 percent of the sample was drawn i.e. 231 respondents were interviewed depending on their availability and willingness to take interviews that included 16 Inspectors, 31 Sub-Inspectors, 41 Assistant Sub-Inspectors and 143 Head Constables. There were two Inspectors each in three police stations in Sector 17, Sector 19 and Manimajra police stations. It was decided to take one Inspector from each of these police stations. A structured interview schedule was used to collect information.

In the present study, the term 'job satisfaction' has been to show a combination of the employee's perceptions towards the different aspects of the job. The four indicators namely financial, working conditions, work policies and public image were used to measure the level of job satisfaction.

- (1) Financial aspect of job included salary, overtime, pension and retirement benefit and family financial security.
- (2) Working conditions related to infra structure such as air condition and lightening, necessary equipment, quality of equipment, adequate supervisory support /backing and working hours.
- (3) Work Policies of the police Department focussed transfer, holidays ,vacation time ,etc., Promotion system , opportunities for professional growth , Grievance redressal system, Satisfaction with due credit to capabilities.
- (4) Public image highlighted current method of filling report, public image, feeling proud of working in this police department, public dealing of the police and police public ratio.

Keeping in mind these four aspects level of job satisfaction was measured. To measure the level of job satisfaction of the respondents, statements from Minnesota job satisfaction scale were adapted. It included 20 statements. The responses to each statement were rated on five point Likert scale. All the 20 statements were rated on five point Likert scale.

Results

Socio-demographic profile

It was found that 56.2 percent Inspectors, 76.2 percent Head Constables, 58.1 percent Sub Inspectors and 46.3 percent ASIs were above the age of 50 years. 58.3 percent respondents were from general caste background and 74.4 percent respondents belonged to Hindu religion. Majority of Head Constables were educated up to High School and majority of Inspectors were either Graduate or Post Graduate. 14.7 percent Head Constables, 29.3 percent ASIs, 32.3 percent Sub-Inspectors and 87.5 percent Inspector rank officials were Graduates. 70.9 percent respondents belonged to rural background. All the respondents were married but very few spouses of the respondents were working. 96.9 percent of the respondents were residing in nuclear household and had small family. Although a majority of the spouses of the respondents were educated they were not engaged in any kind of paid work. A majority of respondents had children of both sexes and they were educated and engaged in paid work also.

Level of job satisfaction

In general, all personnel in an organization are neither wholly content nor completely dissatisfied with their jobs. There are differences in the respondents' levels of job satisfaction. Job satisfaction is the sense of fulfillment one experiences while working, which serves as motivation. Satisfaction at work, not self-satisfaction, happiness, or contentment, is what matters. Twenty statements taken from the Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire were used in an effort to gauge how satisfied the respondents were with their jobs. On a five-point scale ranging from very low to very high, all of the respondents were asked to express their opinions on these 20 statements. To allow for variances in responses, the responses to each statement were pre-coded as very low, low, average, high, and very high. Different scores were assigned to their responses in order to determine each individual's cumulative standing. These were further divided into the Low, Medium, and High categories.

Table No. 1 Distribution showing level of job satisfaction of the respondents

Level of satisfaction	Frequency	Percentage
Low	108	(46.8%)
Medium	62	(26.8%)
High	61	(26.4%)
Total	231	(100)

Table No. 1 shows that out of the total 231 respondents, 46.8 percent had a low level of job satisfaction. Most of the respondents were over the age of 50 and reported low levels of job satisfaction. The data also indicates that 26.8 percent of respondents had a medium level of job satisfaction. There were 26.4 percent of respondents who had a high level of job satisfaction. Such findings indicate that more respondents were not satisfied with their jobs. There are several factors that contribute to police officers' low level of job satisfaction, including high levels of stress, poor communication with superiors, a lack of recognition, few opportunities for professional advancement, etc. When there is little room for flexibility or another source of inspiration for the workers, dissatisfaction may also develop. Employees want their employers to acknowledge their accomplishments at work. Lower-ranking police officers frequently feel forgotten and unimportant since higher-ranking officers in the department rarely give them recognition. Rank and level of job satisfaction. The rank positions in the police organization range from DIG to constable. The higher-ranking officers work in a supervisory and controlling capacity. The junior or subordinate officers include inspectors or sub-inspectors, assistant sub-inspectors, head constables, and constables. For the present study, top-ranking officials and constables have been purposefully excluded from the study. It is asserted that there is a close relation between rank and job satisfaction. With the increase in rank/ Rank, qualification and salary, job satisfaction also increases (Gurbuz, 2007; Metle, 2001; Ronen, 1978). Bertz and Judge, 1994) report negligible relationship between rank and job satisfaction. Rank is one of the determinants of job satisfaction (Dantzker, 1994 & Hunt and McCadden, 1985). Lower rank police officers have the lowest level of job satisfaction as compared to other police officials. Bastemur (2006) on the other hand reports that rank does not have a significant effect on job satisfaction. Sheley and Nock (1979) state that the negative relationship between police officials' seniority and their level of job satisfaction. Miller et al. (2009) argue that rank has negative relation with job satisfaction for police officials' .As they move up the ladder, their perception of job satisfaction disappears. An attempt was made to know the rank wise level of job satisfaction of the respondents.

Table No. 2 Rank wise distribution showing level of job satisfaction of the respondents

Level of satisfaction	Rank								Total
	Head Constable	ASI	Sub Inspector	Inspector					
Low	68 (47.6%)	20 (48.8%)	14 (45.2%)	6 (37.5%)	108				(46.8%)
Medium	35 (24.5%)	13 (31.7%)	10 (32.3%)	4 (25%)	62				(26.8%)
High	40 (28%)	8 (19.5%)	7 (22.6%)	6 (37.5%)	61				(26.4%)
Total	143 (100)	41 (100)	31 (100)	16 (100)	231				(100)

Table no.2 reveals that 47.6 percent Head Constables, 48.8 percent ASIs, 45.2 percent Sub Inspectors and 37.5 percent Inspectors had low level of job satisfaction. Further analysis highlighted that police officials who were posted at Industrial area and sector 11 police stations had low level satisfaction. These police stations are hub of activity mainly due to large population in adjoining areas; police men posted in these police stations are overworked. While 24.5 percent Head Constables, 31.7 percent ASIs, 32.3 percent Sub Inspectors and 25 Inspectors reported medium level of job satisfaction. There were 28 percent Head Constables, 19.5 percent ASIs, 22.6 percent Sub Inspectors and 37.5 percent Inspectors who had high level of job satisfaction. The results partially support the findings of Ronen (1978), Gurbuz (2007) and Metle (2001) who state that high rank officials are highly satisfied with their job.

Job Satisfaction

In order to measure Job Satisfaction 20 statements were adapted from Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire were adapted. Job satisfaction was measured on various aspects

Satisfaction	low		medium		high	
salary	44	19%	33	14.3%	154	66.7%
overtime	174	75.3%	21	9.1%	36	15.6%
retirement benefits	121	52.4%	33	14.3%	77	33.3%
financial security	51	22.1%	23	10%	157	68%
working	140	60.6%	18	7.8%	73	31.6%

conditions						
equipment	114	49.4%	24	10.4%	93	40.3%
quality equipment	151	65.4%	19	8.2%	62	26.4%
Support System	126	54.5%	93	40.3%	02	0.9%
Working schedule	150	64.9%	27	11.7%	54	23.4%
Transfers	91	39.4%	33	14.3%	107	46.3%
Holidays,leave	181	78.4%	22	9.5%	28	12.1%
Promotion system	166	71.9%	14	6.1%	51	22.1%
Adequate opportunities	124	53.7%	29	12.6%	78	33.8%
Grievance settlement	122	52.8%	30	13%	79	34.2%
recognition	96	41.6%	26	11.3%	109	47.2%
Filing reports	105	45.5%	21	9.1%	105	45.5%
Public image	125	54.1%	33	14.3%	73	31.6%
Working within dept	101	43.7%	27	11.7%	103	44.6%
Public dealing	119	51.5%	34	14.7%	78	33.8%
Public-police ratio	125	54.1%	33	14.3%	73	31.6%

The results show that only 19 percent of respondents showed low levels of job satisfaction with the current basic pay and salary increase. It is quite astonishing to note that most of the respondents, i.e., 66.7 percent, had a high level of job satisfaction with their current basic pay and salary increase. On further inquiry, it was revealed that a majority of them had additional sources of income. A few respondents reported that they have private businesses. A few others revealed that they have rental income. Others disclosed that they have agricultural land as a part of parental property. Results show that a majority of the Sub Inspectors i.e. 83.9 percent followed by 75.6 percent respondents had low levels of job satisfaction with regard to compensation for overtime. They reported that they don't get any compensation from the department and have to manage the expenses on their own. Such findings endorse views of Sigler and Wilson (1988). Most of the respondents who reported high levels of satisfaction were from Inspector rank. It is important to mention that a large number of inspectors reported that they have additional sources of income, so they don't mind even when they are not paid

compensation for overtime. A little more than fifty percent of the respondents, i.e., 52.4%, had a low level of job satisfaction with regard to pensions, retirement benefits, etc. They reported that they give their youth and the prime of their lives to society; however, the compensation they get for their sacrifices is not appropriate. Results reveals that 22.1 percent respondents had low levels of job satisfaction with regard to financial security in their job whereas 68 percent respondents had high levels of job satisfaction with regard to financial security in their job. Results depict that 60.6 percent respondents reported low levels of job satisfaction with regard to working conditions and 31.6 percent respondents reported high levels of job satisfaction with regard to working conditions and a majority of respondents were of rank of Inspector. The reason could be that because the inspector is the head of the police station, he has all the power and facilities, which is why a higher number of inspectors showed a high level of satisfaction with working conditions. Results reveal that most of the respondents had low level of satisfaction with regard to their working conditions. The findings show that 49.4 percent of respondents showed low levels of satisfaction with the tools and resources needed to perform their jobs effectively. The lack of modern tools, such as high-tech vehicles, guns, wireless phones, etc., among police officers' equipment, may be the cause. There were, however, 40.3 percent respondents who had high level of job satisfaction with regard to equipment and resources. out of 65.4 percent respondents that included 66.4 percent Head Constables, 58.5 percent ASIs, 67.7 percent Sub Inspectors and 68.8 percent Inspectors had low level of job satisfaction with quality of equipment. The reason could be police officials don't have technological wireless phone, gun and vehicle for patrolling. There were 26.4 percent respondents that included 25.2 percent Head Constables, 31.7 percent ASIs, 22.6 percent Sub Inspectors and 31.2 percent Inspectors who reported high level of satisfaction with regard to quality of equipment. There were 8.2 percent respondents who reported medium level of job satisfaction with quality of weapon. results reveal that 54.5 percent respondents that included 53.8 percent Head Constables, 56.1 percent ASIs, 58.1 percent Sub Inspectors and 50 percent Inspectors had low level of satisfaction with regard to support system. They reported that their Superiors assign them work without any guidance. There is no input from super-ordinates. In case they fail in completing the task accurately onus lies on them, however, when they complete the assignment on time they don't get any appreciation. It is pertinent to mention here that most of these respondents had uncordial relations with their super-ordinates. There were 40.3 percent respondents that included 42

percent Head Constables, 36.6 percent ASIs, 35.5 percent Sub Inspectors and 43.8 percent Inspectors who had medium level of satisfaction with support system that they are getting in their work place. Only 2.4 percent ASIs and 6.2 percent Inspectors reported high level of satisfaction with regard to support system. Results reveal that most the respondents were disgruntled with support system and it may influence their job satisfaction. out of 64.9 percent respondents, 64.3 percent Head Constables, 68.3 percent ASIs, 64.5 percent Sub Inspectors and 62.5 percent Inspectors had low level of satisfaction with regard to work schedule. These respondents reported that they have to work long hours and many a times without break. They argued that they are always on duty on festivals. They also wish to spend time with their families on these occasions. Additionally they are also assigned duties during rallies, strikes and VIP security. Most of the respondents who reported low level of satisfaction with work schedule belonged to Mauli Jagran police station, Sector 36 police station, Sector 34 police station, Industrial area police station and Sarngpur police station. There were only 23.4 percent respondents who reported high level of satisfaction with regard to work schedule. Results reveal that most of the respondents reported that they had low level of job satisfaction with work schedule and it influences the job satisfaction level. Results show that 39.4 percent respondents that included 39.2 percent Head Constables, 46.3 percent ASIs, 35.5 percent Sub Inspectors and 31.2 percent Inspectors who had low level of satisfaction with the process of interdepartmental transfers. There were 14.3 percent respondents who had medium level of satisfaction with the process of interdepartmental transfers. There were 48.3 percent Head constables, 41.5 percent ASIs, 41.9 percent Sub Inspectors and 50 Inspectors who reported high level of job satisfaction with the process of interdepartmental transfers because they didn't find any anomaly in the process of the transfers. They argued that routine transfers help in breaking the hold of particular Officer. Results reveal that a majority of the respondents i.e. 78.4 percent had low level of job satisfaction with current benefits: holidays, personal days, vacation time, etc. Results also reveal those high rank officials including 81.2 percent Inspectors, 83.9 percent Sub Inspectors and 85.4 percent ASIs and 74.8 percent Head Constables reported low level of satisfaction with current benefits: holidays, personal days, vacation time etc. They reported that police job is very hectic; they rarely work less than 12 hours a day. They are on duty on festivals days and many a times their leave is cancelled and they called back on duty because of some VIP duties. The weekly off is also not definite as there could an additional work or contingency in the city. There

were only 12.1 percent respondents who had high level of job satisfaction with current benefits: holidays, personal days, vacation time etc. There were 13.3 percent Head Constables, 12.2 percent ASIs, 9.7 percent Sub Inspectors and 6.2 percent Inspectors had high level of job satisfaction with current benefits: holidays, personal days, vacation time, etc. Results reveal that most of the respondents were not satisfied with current benefits: holidays, personal days, vacation time etc. Results reveal that 80.5 percent ASIs, 68.5 percent Head Constables, 80.6 percent Sub Inspectors and 62.5 percent Inspectors showed low level of job satisfaction with current promotion system. They reported that their senior officials are biased. The talent, merit and performance of the officers are not recognized by the department. It is unfortunate that the honest, sincere and hardworking police officials are not recognized. These officials have served police department for many years with few promotion. Most of the respondents were above the age of 50 years and they belonged to general caste. While there were 19.4 percent Sub Inspectors, 31.2 percent Inspectors, 14.6 percent ASIs and 23.8 percent Head Constables who showed high level of satisfaction with current promotion system. The possible reason could be that these officials got timely promotion. Results reveal that a majority of the respondents showed dissatisfaction with current promotion system. Results show that 47.6 percent Head Constables, 70.7 percent ASIs, 54.8 percent Sub Inspectors and 62.5 percent Inspectors showed low level of satisfaction with the adequate opportunities to develop professionally (i.e. workshop, training courses and conferences). They reported that they were overburdened and their busy schedule does not allow them to attend any workshop and training. Results reveal that 52.8 percent respondents that included 55.2 percent Head Constables, 53.7 percent ASIs, 45.2 percent Sub Inspectors and 43.8 percent Inspectors showed low level of satisfaction with regard to grievance settlement procedure in the police department. There were only 13 percent respondents who had medium level of satisfaction with regard to grievance settlement Procedure in the police department. Above table depicts that 41.6 percent respondents that included 42.7 percent Head Constables, 46.3 percent ASIs, 35.5 percent Sub Inspectors and 31.2 percent Inspectors who reported low level of satisfaction with police department policy of giving due credit to their capabilities. They argued that right person is not posted at right place. They reported that there is a corruption in the department, the super-ordinates place their favourite officials at their desired positions. Those who are not in the good books of the authorities are given odd postings. Experience and capabilities are not recognized by senior officials. There

were 47.2 percent respondents that included 46.9 percent Head Constables, 46.3 percent ASIs, 41.9 percent Sub Inspectors and 62.5 percent Inspectors who reported high level of satisfaction with regard to police department policy on giving due credit to their capabilities. There were 11.3 percent respondents who had medium level of satisfaction. Since more respondents showed satisfaction on how police department recognizes capabilities of its officials. These respondents were getting due weightage of their capabilities. They reported that their talent and skill is fully appreciated and recognized by their seniors and they are accordingly rewarded. Therefore they admitted that police department places right person at right place.

Discussion

Job satisfaction is a significant aspect of work. It is believed that individuals who experience greater Job satisfaction are healthier mentally and physically. Job satisfaction is a serious issue with regard to police organization due to nature of its work. A police force is a service-intensive organization with a significant proportion of its employees working in direct contact with the general public. Different jobs subject police officers to various working conditions that call for various physical and psychological capabilities to deal with problems. When dealing with such risky situations, police organisations demand a high level of productivity and efficiency from their staff. However, police officials encounter a variety of challenges that negatively impact their ability to do their jobs, including a hostile work environment, lengthy workdays, delayed promotions, a lack of autonomy, tense interpersonal relationships at work, political interference, disturbed personal life, etc. In order to streamline the police force and implement initiatives that will improve it, the Indian government is implementing a variety of changes. Despite the improvements, the quality of the Indian police's service delivery has continued to decline while daily crime rates rise. Every citizen unquestionably expects more from the police than he is now receiving. But the majority of citizens claim that the cops are dishonest, unfriendly, and harassing. The present study tries Findings indicate that more respondents had low level of job satisfaction whereas there was hardly any difference in respondents with moderate and low level of job satisfaction. Further it was noted that lower rank officials had low level of job satisfaction. The results partially support the findings of Ronen (1978), Gurbuz (2007) and Metle (2001) who state that high rank officials are highly satisfied with their job. Job satisfaction scale was adapted from Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire was used. Further job satisfaction was measured on

various aspects, financial benefits, working conditions, work policies and public image. Under each component different statements were given.

Results reveal that a large number of respondents were satisfied with their salary which negate the findings of Dantzker & Surette, (1996). Higher rank officials reported greater financial satisfaction whereas lower rank officials had low level of job satisfaction with regard to pension, retirement benefits etc. Results reveal that most of the respondents had low level of satisfaction with regard to their working conditions. Findings endorse the views of Robbins (1996) & Yun et al. (2015). Low rank officials had low level of job satisfaction with regard to equipment and resources. Results support Suresh et al. (2013) who mention that poor equipment results in dissatisfaction among policemen. A majority of respondents had low level of job satisfaction with quality of equipment. Results reveal that most the respondents were disgruntled with support system that influences their job satisfaction which coincides with findings of Pursley (1974) and Gyamfi (2014). Results reveal that most of the respondents reported that they had low level of job satisfaction with work schedule, which coincide with findings of Malach – Pines and Kienan, 2007; McCarthy et al. 2007. Most of the respondents had high level of job satisfaction with the process of interdepartmental transfers because they didn't find any anomaly in the process of the transfers. Results negate the findings of Lall (2010) who reported that postings are misused power.

Results reveal that a majority of the respondents had low level of job satisfaction with current benefits: holidays, personal days, vacation time, etc. thus support findings of Demerouti et al. 2004 & Maheshwari, 1978 . Results reveal that a majority of the respondents showed dissatisfaction with current promotion system and it may influence their level of job satisfaction which coincides with the findings of Getahum et al. (2007); Gilstrap & Collins, (2012) and Reiss (1967).

Most of the respondents had low level of satisfaction with the adequate opportunities to develop professionally. Further low rank officials had low level of satisfaction with regard to grievance settlement procedure in the police department. Similarly low rank officials reported low level of satisfaction with police department policy of giving due credit to their capabilities.

Results show that high rank officials reported medium level of job satisfaction with regard to current methods of filling reports. Results reveal that most of the respondents except Inspector

rank officials had low level of satisfaction with regard to public image which partially support Skolnick (1966) and Balch (1972) & Wood (1997).

Sub Inspectors and Inspectors reported high level of satisfaction for working in police department. Results support findings of Krimmel & Tartaro (1994). Most of the respondents were not contented with public dealing of police thus support with the findings of the Hoath et al. (1998). Overworked low rank officials had low level of job satisfaction with public police ratio.

Conclusion

Job satisfaction related research among personnel in criminal justice system is new as compared to employees in other professions. Police personnel play a vital role in maintaining the corrective and statutory balance in the society. However, police work has been viewed as one of the most tiring and stressful jobs because of nature of work. Further in poor countries like India, low public police ratio, political interference and lack of infra structure makes it all the more cumbersome. In this light present study has been undertaken.

References

- Agho, A.O., Mueller, C.W., & Price, J.L. (1993). "Determinants of employee job satisfaction". *Journal of Human Relations*, Vol. 46, No.(8), pp.80-85.
- Bastemur, Y., (2006), "İş Tatmini İle Yaşam Tatmini Arasındaki İlişkiler: Kayseri Emniyet Müdürlüğü"nde Bir Araştırma". Unpublished Master Thesis. The Erciyes University, Social Sciences Institute, Kayseri, Turkey. Cited in purl.fcla.edu/fcla/etd/CFE0002238
- Bedeian, A.G., Ferris, G.R. & Kacmar, K.M. (1992). "Age, tenure and job satisfaction: A tale of two perspectives." *Journal of Vocational Behaviour*, Vol. 40, No.(1), pp.33-48.
- Bennett, Richard. R (1997). "Excessive force: A Comparative Study of Police in the Caribbean." *Justice Quarterly*, Vol.14, No. (4), pp.651-681.
- Bertz, R. D. Jr., & Judge, T. A. (1994). "Person-organization fit and the theory of work adjustment: Implications for satisfaction, tenure, and career success." *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, Vol.44, No.(1), pp. 32-54.
- Buzawa, E., Austin, T., Bannon, J. (1994). "The Role of Selected Socio-Demographic and Job-Specific Variables in Predicting Patrol Officer Job Satisfaction: A Re-examination Ten Years Later." *American Journal of Police*, Vol.13, No.(2), pp.51-75.
- Clark et al. (1996) Clark, A., Oswald, A. & Warr, P. (1996), "Is job satisfaction U-shaped in age?" *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology*, Vol.69, No.(1), pp. 57-81.
- Dantzker (1994) Dantzker, M.L. (1994). "Measuring job satisfaction in Police Departments and Policy Implications: An Examination of a mid-size, Southern Police Department." *American Journal of Police*, Vol.13, No.(2), pp. 77-101.
- Gurbuz, A. (2007). An assessment on the effect of education level on the job satisfaction from the tourism sector point of view]. *Dogus Universitesi Dergisi*, 8, 36-46. Retrieved from [http://ijbssnet.com/journals/Vol._2_No._5_\[Special_Issue_-_March_2011\]/11.pdf](http://ijbssnet.com/journals/Vol._2_No._5_[Special_Issue_-_March_2011]/11.pdf) on dated 21.01.2016

- Hoath, D. R., Schneider, F. W., & Starr, M. W. (1998). "Police Job Satisfaction as a function of Career Orientation and Position Tenure: Implications for Selection and community policing." *Journal of Criminal Justice*, Vol. 26, No.(4), pp. 337-347.
- Hunt, R.G. & McCadden, K.S. (1985). "A Survey of Work Attitudes of Police Officers: Commitment and Satisfaction." *Police Studies*, Vol. 8, No.(1), pp. 17-25.
- Johnson (2012) Johnson, R.R. (2012), "Police officer's job satisfaction: a multidimensional analysis." *Police Quarterly*, Vol. 15, No. (2), pp. 157-176.
- Kanchana V, Vijayalakshmi R, Sudha M.(2012). "Job satisfaction and work stress of traffic police-a study in Salem city, Tamilnadu". *Asian Pacific Research Business Management* .Vol.3,No.(2),pp.34-39.
- Kang, W. and Nalla, M.K. (2011). "Perceived citizen cooperation, police operational philosophy, and job satisfaction on support for civilian oversight of the police in South Korea." *Asian Journal of criminology*. Vol.6, No.(2),pp.177-189.
- Lee, Chang-Hun and Moon, Junseob (2011). "Effects of officers' cynicism and their perception of managerial leadership on COP activities among South Korean police officers." *Policing: An International Journal of Strategies and Management*, Vol.34, (1),pp.31-48.
- Lord, V.B., Gray, D.; S.B. Pond (1991). "The Police Stress Inventory: Does it measure stress?" *Journal of Criminal Justice*, Vol.19, No.(2), pp. 139-149.
- Metle, M. (2001). "The Impact of Education on Attitudes of Female Government Employees." *The Journal of Management Development*, Vol. 22, No.(7), pp.603-626.
- Miller, H.A. , Mire, S. & Kim, B. (2009). "Predictors of job satisfaction among police officers: Does personality matter?" *Journal of Criminal Justice*, Vol. 37, No.(5) ,pp. 419-426
- Oshagbemi, T. (2000). "Gender differences in the job satisfaction of university teachers." *Women in Management Review*, Vol.15, No. (7),pp. 331-343.
- Ronen, S. (1978) . "Job satisfaction and the neglected variables of job seniority." *Journal of human relations* ,Vol.31, No.(4),pp. 297-308.
- Sheley, J.F. and Nock, S.L (1979). "Determinants of Police Job Satisfaction." *Journal of Sociological Inquiry*, Vol. 49, No. (1), pp. 49-55.
- Spector (1997) Spector, P.E. (1997). *Job Satisfaction: Application, Assessment, Causes and Consequences*. Thousand Oaks, Sage.
- Violanti, J, Marshall, J, Howe, G. (1985). "Stress, Coping and Alcohol Use: the Police Connection." *Journal of Police Science and Administration*, Vol. 13, No.(2), pp.106-110
- Yang, L. R., Yen, H. F., & Chiang, Y. F. (2012). "A framework for assessing impacts of leadership competency on police project performance: mediating role of job satisfaction and moderating role of project type". *Policing: An International Journal of Police Strategies & Management*, Vol. 35, No.(3), pp.528-550.
- Yun, Ilhong ; Hwang, EuiGab and Lynch, James(2015). "Police Stressors, Job Satisfaction, Burnout, and Turnover Intention Among South Korean Police Officers." *Asian Journal of Criminology*, Volume 10, No.(1), pp 23-41.
- Zhao, J., Thurman, Q., He, N. (1999). "Sources of Job Satisfaction among Police Officers: A Test of Demographic and Work Environment Models." *Journal of Justice Quarterly*, Vol. 16, No.(1), pp. 153-173.